

MEASUREMENT OF POLYMERISATION SHRINKAGE OF MATRICES FOR LIQUID MOULDING

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SUMMARY

Matrix shrinkage during liquid moulding of composites is a significant source for residual strains and dimensional instability. The shrinkage of a new thermoplastic matrix for liquid moulding, anionic polyamide-6 during polymerisation, is measured with FBGs and volumetric dilatometry. Parameters governing residual strain formation were identified.

Keywords: Fibre Bragg Gratings, polymerisation shrinkage, anionic polyamide-6, residual strains.

INTRODUCTION

At Delft University of Technology, anionic polymerisation of polyamide-6 is investigated as a thermoplastic matrix for liquid composite moulding (LCM) of composite structures for windmill turbine blades. The main advantages of this thermoplastic matrix are its low price, the rapid polymerisation (1 hour process) and it can be recycled into the initial components. The semi-crystalline nature provides excellent chemical resistance.

One of the topics that remain to be investigated is the development of residual strains in (thick) thermoplastic composite structures manufactured with LCM. During liquid moulding of composites, residual strains start building up when during polymerisation the polymer has developed sufficient stiffness to transfer shrinkage strains to the fibres [1]. If this point can be determined as well as the amount of matrix shrinkage after this point, then it is possible to predict the magnitude of residual strain that will be present in a glass fibre reinforced APA-6 composite laminate after production. An effort was made to identify these two parameters with the aid of Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBGs) and a volumetric shrinkage test.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The APA-6 polymerisation process and its properties were already described elsewhere [2]. Since polymerisation of APA-6 occurs at high temperatures (150-190°C) and the shrinkage tests needs to take place accordingly, two polymer properties that provide a source for residual strain formation can be monitored: polymerisation/ crystallisation shrinkage and thermal contraction upon cooling. Given that no precedent exists for this

material [3], the expected volumetric expansion and shrinkage behaviour of APA-6 with temperature is schematically shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic volume development during polymerisation of APA-6.

Since the caprolactam (CL) monomer comprises 86 mass% of the total mixture, and the initiator and activator (necessary for the polymerisation reaction) are both caprolactam-based as well, it is assumed that the volume and density of the pristine mixture is similar to that of pure caprolactam [3]. The caprolactam-based components are solid at room temperature and upon heating from room temperature (a'), they start to melt at 69.2°C [4], which is indicated in Figure 1 as $T_m(\text{CL})$. The caprolactam solid-liquid transition is accompanied by a significant increase in occupied volume. Both in the solid and liquid phase, the volume increases linearly with temperature [5]. The dotted line between a and $T_m(\text{CL})$ represents the theoretical liquid volume of caprolactam below the melting temperature.

Upon reaching the polymerisation temperature (T_{pol}) at point b , significant shrinkage of the resin occurs accompanied by an increase in temperature caused by the exothermic polymerisation and crystallisation reactions. The shrinkage is largely caused by the difference in number of molecules due to polymerisation: ~ 8850 mmol to $10\text{--}50$ mmol/kg [6]. Crystallisation occurs, because the formed polymer is at a temperature below the crystallisation temperature ($\sim 220^{\circ}\text{C}$) and for lower temperatures the crystallisation rate is higher. Due to the higher density of the crystal phases compared to the amorphous polymer phase [7], the increasing level of crystallinity results in an additional volume decrease.

Upon cooling after the reaction from point c to room temperature, thermal contraction results in additional shrinkage. The slope depends on the degree of crystallinity at point c ; the higher density of the crystal phase compared to the amorphous phase results in a smaller thermal contraction for specimens of higher crystallinity [8, 9]. Upon slow cooling, it is possible that additional crystallisation takes place, since a maximum

driving force for crystallisation of APA-6 exists between 160 and 140°C [3]. In addition, at 70°C the amorphous phases undergo a rubber-to-glass transition temperature (T_g) [10].

In trajectory *b-c* during the polymerisation reaction gelation occurs. The gel-point is the point at which the resin has cured to such an extent that it possesses sufficient mechanical strength to transfer stresses and is therefore useful for the prediction of residual strains [11, 12]. Volume changes prior to polymer gelation are not expected to contribute to residual stress formation, since the polymer is a fluid with low viscosity. Most of the shrinkage is therefore wanted in the liquid state, since replenishment of the monomer can still occur [13].

Test methods

Recent publications describe the use of FBG sensors in ‘single-fibre composites’: a model composite with the optic fibre functioning as fibre reinforcement, while simultaneously detecting the strain development caused by the resin curing shrinkage and thermal contraction [14, 15]. To monitor the strain development and identify transitions during non-isothermal curing, the importance of temperature correction of the strains was pointed out in almost all the publications [11, 16-18]. The gel-point was found to be the point where strain build-up was first detected by the FBG since the resin then has developed sufficient stiffness to enable strain transfer to the optic fibre [17-20]. The FBGs were found suitable for detection of thermal contraction and expansion coefficients, by taking the slope of the strain versus temperature curves [11, 18, 20]. All the investigations in literature used thermosetting and not thermoplastic reactive systems where residual strains were found ranging from -2000 $\mu\epsilon$ to -6000 $\mu\epsilon$. Concluding, the FBG sensors seem a useful tool to establish the matrix contributions to the residual strain development during cure.

In addition, several methods exist to determine the volumetric matrix shrinkage due to polymerisation/ curing and thermal effects. One of these techniques allows monitoring of volumetric changes during the entire cure cycle as in Figure 1 and is based on the buoyancy principle: the volumetric shrinkage test [21]. When a specimen is fully or partially immersed in liquid, buoyancy exerts an upward force on the object/ specimen produced by the surrounding fluid, which equals the weight of the fluid displaced by the body. When the volume of the immersed object reduces while the mass does not (as is the case for a curing polymer), the amount of displaced fluid will decrease, resulting in a lower upward force. Therefore, this technique has the capability of monitoring the volumetric curing shrinkage during the entire curing cycle. This mechanism was recently further developed by Wisnom *et al* [21], where a silicone rubber bag was used that closely followed any volumetric change of the curing polymer resulting in detectable buoyancy variations. In addition, the silicone bag does not adhere to the curing polymer and due to its flexibility is assumed to leave the matrix in a strain-free state.

The volumetric shrinkage test can be used to compare the results obtained with those with the FBG tests, but it can also provide useful information on the total matrix shrinkage before gelation. This information is valuable for determination of the amount

of resin necessary for LCM of composite structures and the prevention of shrinkage porosity and pin-holes.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials

The anionic polyamide-6 matrix was obtained by anionic polymerisation of ϵ -caprolactam, using 1.2mol% caprolactam magnesium bromide (Brüggolen C1) as initiator and 1.2mol% hexamethylene-1,6-dicarbonylcaprolactam as activator (Brüggolen C20). All chemicals were supplied by Brüggemann Chemical, Germany.

The raw materials are supplied in the solid state, and before mixture and subsequent polymerisation they need to be molten. For this purpose a mini mixing unit (MMU) was designed and manufactured by Bronk Industrial BV, Netherlands. In one tank ('tank A') a monomer-activator solution was mixed (mass ratio 88:10) and in the second tank ('tank B') a monomer-initiator solution (mass ratio 39:10), both surrounded by a nitrogen environment at 110°C. When the two solutions were ready, they were mixed (volume ratio 1:1) through a heated static mixer.

Specimen preparation and FBG test set-up

Glass test tubes were filled with the reactive mixture and placed in an oil bath that was set to the required polymerisation temperature (165°C and 175°C). Optic glass fibres with FBG sensors were positioned in the resin-filled tubes, and their wavelength shifts $\Delta\lambda$ due to thermal and strain variations were recorded. The temperature development was registered with a thermocouple. After 45 minutes the test tubes were taken from the oil bath and allowed to cool down to an ambient environment (~21°C).

The fibre optic sensors used for all experiments are Draw Tower fibre Bragg gratings (DTG[®]'s), provided by FBGS-Technologies GmbH, (Germany). The gratings are inscribed in the core of a Single mode optical fibre with core and cladding diameter of 6 and 125 μm , respectively. The optic fibres contained two 4 mm long gratings with Bragg wavelengths of 1558 and 1563 nm, respectively and were coated with an Ormocer[®] coating (ORganically MOdified CERamic coating with outer diameter 195 μm) as supplied by FOS&S, Belgium.

Strain-free, or FBG temperature sensors are required for temperature compensation in the case of non-isothermal strain determination with FBG sensors. For this purpose, the 1563 nm Bragg grating was surrounded by a 40 mm long stainless steel (AISI 304) capillary with inner diameter 0.6 mm and outer diameter 1.0 mm, which was sealed at the extremities with high temperature resistant epoxy glue, Epotek[®] 353ND (Gentec, Belgium). A tiny polyimide tape was used to seal the gap between the optic fibre and the capillary during gluing. A metal capillary was chosen for its good thermal conductivity and there is no affinity (static attraction) of the optic fibre towards the metal surface of capillary, unlike with a glass ferrule [22].

The optic fibres and strain-free sensors were cleaned with ethanol and connected to an FBG-Scan616 interrogator (FOS&S, Belgium). Reference wavelengths were recorded at room temperature to determine the initial Bragg wavelengths of the gratings, λ_B^0 .

Cleaned K-type thermocouples were used and connected to a Keithley data logging device. Data acquisition frequency was 5 seconds (0.2 Hz).

The (linear) strain $\Delta\varepsilon_{lin}$ can be calculated with Equation 1, where the strain coefficient $(1-P) = 0.78$ and S and T denote the measurements for the strain and temperature FBG sensors, resp.:

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{lin} = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_B^0}\right)_S - \left(\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_B^0}\right)_T}{(1-P)} \quad (1)$$

Volumetric shrinkage test set-up

First, the hand-made silicone (Silastic-M® RTV from Dow Corning, USA) bags and seals were preheated at 110°C in an oven. A glass beaker was filled with the reactive APA-6 mixture directly from the Mini-Mixing Unit (MMU) and this was used to fill the silicone bags by means of a syringe. The oil bath was heated to the desired polymerisation temperature (160, 170 and 180°C) and the polymer resin filled silicone bag was carefully suspended in the oil bath and attached to a balance positioned above the oil bath. After ~60 minutes, the heater of the oil bath was switched off and the polymer was allowed to cool to room temperature to enable studying of the thermal contraction after polymerisation. For every polymerisation temperature, at least two experiments were carried out.

Some problems showed during testing: the silicone bag absorbed the oil at the high temperatures and this affected the measurements significantly. Fortunately, the oil permeation did not affect the polymerisation of the APA-6 resin. Corrections for this have been made, but not conclusively and therefore only qualitative results were obtained.

The polymer volumetric shrinkage is given by Equation 2:

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{pol} = \frac{\Delta V_{pol}}{V_{pol}^0} = \frac{V_{pol}^1 - V_{pol}^0}{V_{pol}^0} \quad (2)$$

Where V_{pol} equals [23]

$$V_{pol} = \frac{m_{pol} - m_{pol}^{bal}}{\rho_{fl}} = \frac{m_{pol} - m_{tot}^{bal} + m_{bag}^{bal}}{\rho_{fl}} \quad (3)$$

For sake of clarity, every parameter in Equation 3 is discussed separately:

- The polymer mass can be assumed to remain constant during the reaction, and therefore $m_{pol}^0 = m_{pol}^1$ (where the 0 and 1 represent the test reference time and any time during the test, respectively). The polymer mass is determined after the test is performed by means of a balance.
- The mass of the entire submersed assembly m_{tot}^{bal} (silicone bag with polymer) is registered by the balance during the test.

- The buoyancy fluid density ρ_{fl} varies with temperature. The heat controller modulates the temperature around the set temperature and therefore the oil temperature fluctuates during testing. This has a significant effect on the fluid density, which therefore needs to be established for every data point. This can be accomplished by measuring the oil temperature with a thermocouple and calculating the fluid density with [24]:

$$\rho_{fl} = -0.6507 \cdot T + 902.95 \quad (4)$$

- The most problematic parameter is the contribution of the silicone bag on the total submersed mass as registered by the balance during the test, m_{bag}^{bal} . Two effects play a significant role: thermal expansion and shrinkage of the silicone rubber with temperature variations, and oil absorption. To gain insight in the development of m_{bag}^{bal} during the test, a clean empty silicone bag was suspended below the balance in the oil and exposed to a similar thermal cycle as during the APA-6 polymerisation tests, where the effect of additional temperature increase due to the polymer's exothermal reaction is neglected. In addition, the silicone bags were made by hand and can therefore differ in weight and local thickness, which can result in significant differences in m_{bag}^{bal} values between each test. Therefore, the m_{bag}^{bal} values are not very reliable and unfortunately these values have a paramount effect on the calculated volumetric shrinkage values during the test.
- The reference point V_{pol}^0 is determined by estimating the theoretical liquid caprolactam volume at room temperature ($20^\circ\text{C} = 293.15\text{K}$), point *a* in Figure 1, from the measured polymer mass divided by the theoretical liquid density of caprolactam at room temperature [5]:

$$\rho_{CL} = -4.3586 \cdot 10^{-4} T^2 - 0.67540T + 1074.3 \quad (5)$$

For future tests, the problems with the silicone bags obviously need to be solved to obtain accurate values for volumetric shrinkage development. Since until now no information is available regarding the shrinkage development of APA-6 during polymerisation and crystallisation, it was decided to show the results anyway to gain at least some qualitative insight into the mechanisms governing the APA-6 shrinkage behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In Figure 2 the strain development as detected by the FBGs is displayed against the temperature development. Here, it is clear that the majority of the strain develops after the test tubes were taken from the oil bath (indicated by the arrows), i.e. during cooling from the processing temperature to room temperature. This is also reflected by the higher final strain magnitudes found for the specimens produced at a higher temperature (-2.0 and -2.3% for 166°C to -2.5 and -2.7% for 175°C , resp). Strain development for all specimens starts between 187 and 183°C (gel-point), which coincides with the peak temperatures found for crystallisation (exothermal process). Apparently, the crystallisation process generates the required polymer stiffness for strain transfer. No rubber-to-glass transition (T_g) could be observed.

Figure 2. Development of strain with temperature for APA-6.

Volumetric shrinkage

The shrinkage is plotted against the temperature for several specimens in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Volumetric shrinkage profiles with temperature for APA-6 specimens polymerised at different temperatures

This graph can be divided in several parts, based on Figure 1:

- **a-b** represents the thermal expansion of the unreacted polymer mixture upon heating to the polymerisation temperature. For all specimens this behaviour is

similar (i.e. when the curves are shifted over the temperature axis, they will coincide). The non-linearity is attributed to the influence of the silicone bag.

- **b-c** signifies the polymerisation and crystallisation shrinkage at the curing temperature. The total amount of shrinkage before cooling varies significantly (points *c* are indicated by the arrows), but the results show that most of the polymerisation + crystallisation shrinkage for the specimens cured at 172 and 162°C, occurs before the peak temperature is reached, while for the specimens produced at higher temperatures, significant shrinkage was still observed after.
- **c-d** represents the thermal shrinkage upon cooling from the polymerisation temperature. Here, a somewhat non-linear behaviour is observed, which corresponds to literature on this topic [25] as well as the FBG results. The specimen cured at the lowest temperature shows the most shallow slope, which can be attributed to a higher level of crystallinity. No rubber-to-glass transition temperatures T_g can be distinguished for any of the specimens.

The parts that can form a contribution to residual strain formation are *b-c* and *c-d*. For part *b-c* it was identified with FBGs that the crystallisation shrinkage is of most significance. However, it is very difficult to separate the polymerisation and crystallisation shrinkage contributions. Hence for every specimen, the volumetric shrinkage caused by polymerisation + crystallisation between points *b* and *c* is calculated with Equation 6, and the thermal contraction upon cooling from the processing temperature between points *c* and *d* is calculated with equation 7:

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{vol}^{(b-c)} = \frac{V_{pol}^c - V_{pol}^b}{V_{pol}^b} \quad (6),$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{vol}^{c-d} = \frac{V_{pol}^d - V_{pol}^c}{V_{pol}^c} \quad (7)$$

The volume at point *d* is taken at 40°C, because for this temperature the data were available for all specimens. The results are shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4. Polymerisation + crystallisation shrinkage (*b-c*) and thermal contraction upon cooling (*c-d*) for APA-6 specimens processed at different temperatures.

It is clear from Figure 4 that trajectory *b-c* is highest for the 162°C polymerisation temperature, which is caused by the combined polymerisation and crystallisation at this lower temperature. At higher temperatures, lower degrees of crystallisation and conversion are obtained, which is reflected by the lower amount of shrinkage between points *b* and *c*. The significant variation for the last three specimens can be explained by side-reactions caused by the high temperatures, resulting in inhomogeneous polymerisation. Even though the values are not reliable, this test shows that the APA-6 polymer shrinks significantly (~10%) during polymerisation.

Thermal contraction upon cooling (*c-d*) was found to increase with polymerisation temperature, similar to the FBG results.

CONCLUSIONS

This research showed that residual strain development during processing of APA-6 can be detected by means of fibre Bragg gratings. It was found that with the FBGs it is possible to identify the point where the polymer is capable of transferring strains, as well as the (linear) strain development from that point onwards. For the APA-6 this point was observed close to the crystallisation temperature. Final residual strain values at room temperature ranged from -2.0 to -2.7%, where the higher values corresponded to higher processing temperatures.

A relatively simple and cheap test set-up was prepared in-house for volumetric shrinkage analysis of anionically polymerising thermoplastic APA-6 polymer, which is currently developed for application in composite wind-mill turbine blades. Qualitative analysis of the volumetric shrinkage results showed that the APA-6 polymer shrinks significantly due to polymerisation, which may cause voids or pinholes in composites. Moreover, the shrinkage upon cooling from the processing temperature to room temperature was higher for specimens manufactured at higher temperatures. This can be attributed to the postponed effect of crystallisation. At temperatures of 175°C and higher, a large variety of curves was shown, which was related to the competing kinetics of polymerisation, side-reactions, and crystallisation.

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References

1. Favre, J.P., Residual thermal stresses in fibre reinforced composite materials - A review. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Materials*, 1(1-4): 37-53, 1988.
2. van Rijswijk, K., Thermoplastic Composite Wind Turbine Blades. 2007. PhD thesis Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology, Delft. 249 pages.
3. van Geenen, A.A., Vragen n.a.v. verklaren resultaten in proefschrift P. Parlevliet, recipient: Parlevliet, P.P. 10 december 2008. Personal correspondence.

4. DSM_Fibre_Intermediates. Product Data Sheet - Caprolactam A.P. Quality (flakes). 2008 July 1998 [cited 2008 15 December 2008]; DFI 7/98.
5. Pure component properties - Caprolactam. 1993, DSM.
6. van Geenen, A.A., Opmerkingen n.a.v. afstudeerverslag van Pieter Verburg: "development of techniques for polymer shrinkage measurement", Parlevliet, P.P., Editor. 2008, AvG Consultancy. p. 2.
7. Bessell, T.J., Hull, D., Shortall, J.B., The effect of polymerization conditions and crystallinity on the mechanical properties and fracture of spherulitic nylon 6. *Journal of Materials Science*, 10: 1127-1136, 1975.
8. Baltá Calleja, F.J., Fakirov, S., Effect of Crystallinity on hardness, in *Microhardness of Polymers*, Clarke, D.R., Suresh, S., and Ward, I.M., Editors. 2000, Cambridge University Press: Cambridge. p.90-94.
9. Callister, W.D.J., Thermal Expansion, in *Materials Science and Engineering - An Introduction*. 2000, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: New York. p.661-664.
10. van Geenen, A.A., Anionic Polyamide - Chemistry and processing. 2007, AvG Consultancy.
11. Antonucci, V., *et al.*, Cure-induced residual strain build-up in a thermoset resin. *Composites Part A-Applied Science And Manufacturing*, 37(4): 592-601, 2006.
12. Madhukar, M.S., Genidy, M.S., Russell, J.D., A new method to reduce cure-induced stresses in thermoset polymer composites, part I: Test method. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 34(22): 1882-1904, 2000.
13. Verstegen, E.J.K., *et al.*, Influence of the reaction mechanism on the shape accuracy of optical components obtained by photoreplication. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 90(9): 2364-2376, 2003.
14. Colpo, F., Humbert, L., Botsis, J., Characterisation of residual stresses in a single fibre composite with FBG sensor. *Composites Science and Technology*, 67(9): 1830-1841, 2007.
15. Yong, W., Bongtae, H. Measurement of effective chemical shrinkage of polymeric materials using fiber bragg grating sensor. in *Proceedings of the International Symposium and Exhibition on Advanced Packaging Materials Processes, Properties and Interfaces*. 2007.
16. Chehura, E., *et al.*, Strain development in curing epoxy resin and glass fibre/epoxy composites monitored by fibre Bragg grating sensors in birefringent optical fibre. *Smart Materials & Structures*, 14(2): 354-362, 2005.
17. Cusano, A., *et al.*, Chirped fiber-bragg grating as self-temperature referenced strain sensor in nonisothermal thermoset processing. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 6(1): 111-117, 2006.
18. Harsch, M., Karger-Kocsis, J., Herzog, F., Monitoring of cure-induced strain of an epoxy resin by fiber bragg grating sensor. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 107(2): 719-725, 2008.
19. Antonucci, V., *et al.*, Real time monitoring of cure and gelification of a thermoset matrix. *Composites Science and Technology*, 66(16): 3273-3280, 2006.
20. Giordano, M., *et al.*, Monitoring by a single fiber Bragg grating of the process induced chemo-physical transformations of a model thermoset. *Sensors and Actuators a-Physical*, 113(2): 166-173, 2004.
21. Li, C., *et al.*, In-situ measurement of chemical shrinkage of MY750 epoxy resin by a novel gravimetric method. *Composites Science and Technology*, 64(1): 55-64, 2004.
22. Frövel, M., *et al.*, Performance Evaluation of Fibre Bragg Gratings over a Large Temperature Range, in *5th International Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring*. 2005: Stanford.
23. Parlevliet, P.P., Residual strains in Thick Thermoplastic Composites. 2009. PhD thesis Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology, Delft.
24. Shell Thermia A Technical Data Sheet, Shell Lubricants: Pernis, Netherlands.
25. Kohan, M.I., Dimensional Stability, in *Nylon Plastics Handbook*. 1995, Hanser Publishers: Munich. p.326-333.